

"SEVEN REASONS WHY MEDICINE, PHARMACY AND THE ARTS MAKE US HAPPIER"

Osmanova Maryam Soibkhonovna

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

maryam195018@icloud.com

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Abstract This article describes the fact that art occupies a special place in the life of each person and that we can understand or dislike, understand or bypass. But it is gradually, dripping, thinking about the art that fills us with happiness, special and unlike anything.

Key words: Pharmacy, happiness, dripping, money, comfort life, psychology, understand and dislike.

Аннотация В этой статье описывается тот факт, что искусство занимает особое место в жизни каждого человека и что мы можем понимать или не любить, понимать или обходить стороной. Но это постепенно, каплями, размышления об искусстве, которое наполняет нас счастьем, особенным и ни на что не похожим.

Ключевые слова: аптека, счастье, капельница, деньги, комфортная жизнь, психология, понимать и не любить.

There are many things in the world that bring happiness: money, comfort, beautiful clothes, travel. But a separate place in everyone's life is occupied by art. We can understand it or dislike it, understand it or bypass it. But it is art that gradually, drop by drop, fills us with a special and unlike anything happiness.

Pharmacy (pharmacy; lat. pharmacia, Greek φαρμακεία "use, use of medicines, medicines", from Greek φάρμακον "drug and use of drugs") is a complex of scientific and practical disciplines that study the problems of creation, safety, research, storage, manufacturing, dispensing and marketing of medicinal products, as well as the search for natural sources of medicinal substances. Together with pharmacology, it constitutes the science of drugs.

The term goes back to the ancient Greek concept of "pharmakon" (Greek φάρμακον), which means medicine (that which cures diseases or helps with them) and poison at the same time, which symbolizes one of the oldest principles of medicine: medicine can become poison, and poison in a certain dosage can be medicinal. At the same time, the term pharmaus meant "preparing poison." Since 2013, Russia has celebrated the Day of the Pharmaceutical Industry Worker on May 19. Pharmacy includes sections such as pharmaceutical chemistry, technology of pharmaceutical preparations and dosage forms, forensic chemistry, pharmacognosy, organization and economics of pharmacy, military pharmacy, etc.

Specialists in the field of pharmacy are called pharmacists (secondary specialized education) and pharmacists (higher education).

Pharmaceutical establishments include:

- research institutes
- laboratories Enterprises, manufacturing medicines (pharmaceutical factories)
- institutions responsible for the collection and processing of medicinal plants (procurement divisions and pharmaceutical factories)

- pharmacies and warehouses
- control and analytical laboratories

1. Acts on the body

Research has shown that when we contemplate works of art, we stimulate the motor cortex, the part of the brain that controls body movement. We do not just see the object, but feel it with every cell. We feel paintings, novels, music with our whole body, as if an electric charge passes through us.

2. Reduces stress

Contemplation calms and even heals. One study found that looking at landscapes speeds up the recovery process after surgery. Art has the power to free us from thoughts that repeat day after day, break bad habits, relieve anxiety.

3. Helps understand reality

Art helps us to know and realize three realities: this world, other people and the reality of ourselves. Thanks to guides - artists, poets, musicians, sculptors - we see what others have comprehended before us, and we try to look at this world with different eyes. Through the eyes of the creator.

4. Develops empathy

Empathy is an important gift that helps you understand the feelings of others. Jean Piaget said that we grow up when we learn to see things from other people's point of view. We are not born with this skill, we struggle to master it all our lives.

Art helps us turn on empathy. When we look at the work of an artist or writer, we see the reality of that person. We touch his perception of reality and learn the ways of his self-expression.

5. Teaches you to see

We must admit that sometimes art does not bring us relief. A story can upset, a picture can disturb, music can sadden. But at the same time, art awakens feelings, "heats" them and helps to see something important.

6. Makes you think

Why is Gioconda smiling like that? And why is the heroine of Frida Kahlo saddened? Why does Kandinsky draw circles? Any kind of art - intellectual or decorative - makes us think. Pushes the boundaries, trains the brain, teaches to understand and think. This is not just entertainment or momentary joy, but happiness in a deeper sense.

7. Awakens pleasure

Many of the masterpieces are amazing. Get out of the loop. Frustrated or even angry. But each of the emotions - be it fear, disgust or pain - does not exclude pleasure. That's the way we're made, that's why we love rollercoasters and scary movies. This was known to the Greeks, who once proposed the idea of catharsis: sometimes negative emotions awaken positive sensations.

It's never too late to touch art. Understand, accept, see and appreciate. Buy a ticket to a museum, open a book, go to the theatre. Take the first step and art will fly out to meet you.

References:

- 1.<https://blog.mann-ivanov-ferber.ru/2021/11/21/7-prichin-pochemu-iskusstvo-delaet-nas-schastlivee/>;
- 2.Brockhaus and Efron, 1890-1907;
- 3.Pharmacy Archival copy dated January 20, 2019 at the Wayback Machine // Medical Dictionary Great Soviet Encyclopedia: [in 30 volumes] / ch. ed. A. M. Prokhorov. - 3rd ed. - M.: Soviet Encyclopedia, 1969-1978;
- 4.Great Russian Encyclopedia: [in 35 volumes] / ch. ed. Yu. S. Osipov. - M.: Great Russian Encyclopedia, 2004-2017;
- 5.Sklyarova E. K. History of pharmacy: a short course - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2016-236 p. - ISBN 978-5-222-25469-1 - p. 7;

